

Effect of temperature on the BZ reaction system containing mixed organic substrate in a CSTR

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Effect of temperature on the BZ oscillating reaction system containing bromate-Ce^{IV}-H₂SO₄-oxalic acid and acetone in a Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR) has been studied. Increase in temperature increases the frequency and decreases the amplitude of oscillation. The apparent activation energy for the system is calculated by using the Arrhenius equation.

There are several reports on the effect of temperature on oscillating chemical reactions when studied under batch conditions¹⁻³. The reaction containing bromate-Ce^{IV}-H₂SO₄-mixed organic substrate (oxalic acid and acetone) constitutes one of the types of Belousov-Zhabotinskii oscillating system. There are several BZ reactions containing different combinations of mixed organic substrates⁴⁻⁹. Recently we have started studying these systems in a Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR)^{10,11}. Such studies are becoming important in methods employed in the study of oscillating chemical reactions. In this report, we have studied the oscillatory behavior of the above BZ system at different temperatures in CSTR at one set of inflow composition and flow rate and the apparent activation energy has been calculated.

Results and discussion

The inflow concentrations, the flow rate and the behavior of the system at the different temperatures for which measurements were made are indicated in Fig. 1. It is clear from the above figures that the frequency of oscillations increases with the increase in temperature (time period decreases), while the amplitudes show a maximum at 298 K, and it steadily decreases as the temperature is further increased. As the temperature is one of the environmental factors that has a pronounced effect on the behavior of the basic BZ oscillator, increase in the initial temperature has a pronounced effect on the nature of oscillations. The behavior indicated in these studies points to the possibility of optimum temperatures below and above which the system exhibits a monostable state¹². Since the experiment was run in a CSTR, the oscillations are sustained in nature. The apparent energy of activation (E_a) for the overall process was calculated by using Arrhenius equation at two

temperatures, on the basis that the rate constant is inversely proportional to the time period of oscillations (t) (Table 1). The values indicate that the system is more sensitive to temperature as the temperature is increased.

Fig. 1. Potential traces (A), period (B) and amplitude (C) at different temperatures, inflow concentration and flow rate: $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.02 \text{ M}$, $[\text{oxalic acid}]_0 = 0.05 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+]_0 = 1.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetone}]_0 = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 0.001 \text{ M}$, $k_0 = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}/\text{s}$, $T(^{\circ}\text{K})$: I = 288, II = 298, III = 308 and IV = 318.

Table I. Sulfuric acid- BrO_3^- -oxalic acid-acetone- Ce^{IV} system

Temp.(K)	$1/T \times 10^3$	Period(s)	$\log(1/t)$	E_a (kcal mol $^{-1}$)
288	3.47	240	-2.38	16.69
298	3.35	90	-1.95	19.44
308	3.25	31	-1.49	22.02
318	3.14	10	-1.00	

We have reported earlier⁹ the apparent activation energy for the above BZ system under batch when Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} were the catalysts. The study was done at an initial composition of $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ M}$, $[\text{oxalic acid}] = 0.03 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetone}] = 0.45 \text{ M}$ and $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$ or $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.0005 \text{ M}$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.5 \text{ M}$. The apparent activation energy reported for both were nearly the same with an average value of $17.1 \pm 0.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Nagy *et al.*¹³ have recently reported that the apparent activation energies for some oscillating BZ systems studied showed the dependence on the initial composition used. Further in the case of malonic acid, the apparent activation energy has been indicated to be nearly half in the case of CSTR, when compared to the batch. In the light of these observations further experimental studies at different initial compositions both in CSTR and batch and also efforts to simulate the effect of temperature are in progress.

Experimental

All chemicals were of A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared in 1.5 M sulfuric acid (in double-distilled water). Fig. 2 shows the schematic diagram of the CSTR experimental set up. The inflow solutions are entering into the cell from the bottom and the excess solution going out through the outlet at the top. Two flows were utilized so that the inflow concentration in the reactor was half the

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the CSTR experimental set up: (A) acidic bromate solution reservoir, (B) acid solutions of oxalic acid, acetone and Ce^{IV} solution reservoir, (PP) peristaltic pump, (CSTR) Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor, (CR) chart recorder, (MM) multimeter, (Pt) platinum electrode and (CE) calomel electrode.

concentration of each species in the separate flows. The acidic bromate was taken in one flow and in the other premixed solution of equal volumes of Ce^{IV} , oxalic acid, acetone in the same acidic media were taken. Since the analytical concentration of oxalic acid was higher than the concentration of Ce^{IV} , the latter reduced to Ce^{III} completely. The flow was checked before and after each experiment and the flow rate was considered as the average of the two. The way in which we studied dynamics is starting with an empty reactor vessel. After filling of the reactor volume, potential measurements were made. A peristaltic pump PP20-4C (Miclins India) was used to feed solutions to the cell and this pump had proper arrangements for assuring equal volume from each channel. Smooth bright platinum foil was employed as an indicator electrode, which was inside the CSTR cell and saturated calomel was used as the reference electrode together with 10% KNO_3 (along with Agar-Agar) salt bridge. The whole experiment was carried out at the predetermined temperature using thermostat (Gemini Scientific Industries, Chennai). The signals from the indicator electrode and the reference electrode were fed to Elico-strip chart recorder, LR-103, and a multimeter and also a data card was utilized intermittently for recording the traces. The reaction mixture was stirred with a magnetic stirrer at a speed of 600 rpm; the active volume of the reactor was 30 ml.

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